

SmartDelivery: IoT Platform for Last Mile Delivery Optimization with Real-Time Data and ML-Based Algorithm Selection

Gaetano Carmelo La Delfa¹[0000-0002-1842-5467], Javier Prieto¹[0000-0001-8175-2201], Salvatore Monteleone³[0000-0003-0158-2295], and Hamaad Rafique²[0000-0003-4272-5360]

¹ BISITE Research Group, Faculty of Science, University of Salamanca
calle Espejo s/n, Salamanca, Spain

² Department of Electrical, Electronics and Computer Engineering (DIEEI),
University of Catania, Via Santa Sofia 64, Catania, Italy

³ Niccolò Cusano University, Engineering Department
Via Don Carlo Gnocchi 3, Rome, Italy
{gaetano.ladelfa,javier.prieto}@usal.es,
salvatore.monteleone@unicusano.it, hamaad.rafique@phd.unict.it

Abstract. Last-mile delivery (LMD), the transportation of goods from a distribution hub to the final destination, is the most critical and costly segment of the logistics chain and various strategies have been developed to address its challenges. One class of approaches focuses on optimizing delivery routes for vehicle fleets, a problem known as the Vehicle Routing Problem (VRP). Extensive research has been conducted on novel methodologies and algorithms to solve VRP and its numerous variants. However, these theoretical advances fail to produce the expected results in real-world scenarios due to factors such as inaccurate travel data estimates caused by unpredictable events that may occur during the deliveries. Moreover, driver expertise is typically not considered in route assignment. This paper describes *SmartDelivery*, a novel platform for LMD optimization. We propose a Machine Learning (ML)-based Algorithm Selection (AS) approach to identify the best heuristic or meta-heuristic from a selected portfolio depending on the characteristics of CVRP (Capacitated Vehicle Routing Problem) instances. Furthermore, we describe a method for collecting and processing real-time data to improve travel time estimates between destinations. Lastly, we define a “sixth sense” parameter quantifying drivers’ familiarity with destinations to improve route assignment. The platform is not yet fully implemented. Future research will focus on its practical deployment and validation.

Keywords: Last Mile Delivery · Capacitated Vehicle Routing Problem · Logistics Optimization · Algorithm Selection · Machine Learning.

1 Introduction

Last Mile Delivery (LMD), the final step in the logistics chain, is one of the most critical yet challenging parts of delivery systems. With the growth of e-

Commerce, efficient LMD has become important for both economic and environmental sustainability, as it accounts for roughly 28% of the total transportation cost. Beyond direct costs, LMD produces negative externalities, such as traffic congestion, infrastructure wear, higher accident rates, and pollution [16].

The Vehicle Routing Problem (VRP) [4] and its variants have been extensively studied in the scientific literature to optimize delivery routes. Exact algorithms produce optimal solutions for simple cases, while heuristics, metaheuristics, and hybrid approaches provide high-quality solutions for more complex scenarios [10]. Despite these theoretical advances, the application of VRP algorithms to real-world LMD faces several challenges. Several VRP implementations rely on estimated travel times between destinations from online maps or Geographic Information Systems [7], [12]. However, these static estimates often deviate significantly from real-time values due to dynamic traffic conditions and other unforeseen factors that may arise during trips. Such differences degrade solver performance, making the delivery plan less efficient or sometimes useless. Moreover, route assignment is typically performed randomly, without considering driver-specific expertise regarding destinations and routes. A driver may have extensive knowledge of a particular area, establish relationships with recurring customers, or develop strategies to handle unpredictable challenges during deliveries. This expertise—which we term “*sixth sense*”—is a mix of experience, intuition, and adaptability which contributes to reducing service time and is lost. Finally, algorithm performance varies significantly depending on the characteristics of the VRP instances they are applied to [24], [11], yet limited research exists on automating the selection of the most suitable algorithm for a given problem instance. To address these limitations, this work describes *SmartDelivery*, a novel platform designed for LMD route optimization, which relies on three main components:

1. An ML module for automatic selection of the best heuristic or metaheuristic from a portfolio to solve specific CVRP instances.
2. A novel methodology to exploit real-time vehicle tracking data to accurately estimate travel times between destinations.
3. A mathematical formulation of the driver *sixth sense* concept and its integration into a route assignment model.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 reviews related work on VRP in LMD contexts. Section 3 describes the SmartDelivery architecture. Section 4 summarizes key contributions and outlines future research.

2 Related Work

Numerous VRP variants have been proposed to address specific logistical constraints, such as the VRP with Time Window (VRPTW) [20], which adds service time constraints; the VRP with Pickup and Delivery (VRPPD) [18], which manages both collection and distribution operations; the Multi-Depot VRP (MD-VRP) [13], which considers multiple depots or starting locations; the Dynamic

VRP (DVRP) [14], which accounts for real-time changes in delivery requirements and routing conditions; The Green VRP (GVRP) [6] and the Fuel Consumption VRP (FCVRP) [25] which focus on optimizing routes based on fuel efficiency and carbon emissions. A comprehensive review of VRP models and solving algorithms is presented in the work of Zhang et al. [26]. One of the extensively studied variants is the *Capacitated Vehicle Routing Problem* [21], where each vehicle has a limited capacity, and the goal is to minimize the total travel distance (or some other cost) while ensuring that the total demand of customers served by each vehicle does not exceed its capacity. Exact methods optimally solve simple instances; however, heuristics and metaheuristics become necessary as complexity increases, and no single algorithm consistently outperforms others across all problem configurations [24].

Several studies explored ML for automatic algorithm selection based on instance-specific features. Tuzun et al. [22] employed a simple neural network to identify the most appropriate heuristic for a VRP instance based on its characteristics. Rasku et al. [1] proposed a set of features to characterize CVRP instances, demonstrating their effectiveness in AS. Asín Achá et al. [2] further extended the concept of AS to automatic parameter tuning. In contrast, few studies leverage IoT technology or real-time data to optimize LMD. Jianing et al. [3] proposed a smart, IoT-based, multi-objective green logistics vehicle routing model that integrates real-time sensor data (GPS, RFID, load sensors) to minimize both carbon emissions and transportation costs. Wanganoo et al. [23] designed a framework based on IoT and a mobile app to reduce the delay of deliveries caused by the absence of descriptive delivery addresses in the Middle East. Seongmoon et al. [9] presented a Markov Decision Process-based approach for optimizing driver attendance, departure times, and routing under time-varying traffic conditions, exploiting real traffic data. Furthermore, the role of human factors in LMD has received little attention in research. Deng et al. [5] introduced the VRP with heterogeneous fixed drivers (VRP-HFD), incorporating the unique attributes of drivers (i.e., their regional knowledge and driving qualifications), underscoring the role of such attributes in optimizing LMD. Schneider et al. [19] propose a VRPTW with driver-specific times to reflect the knowledge of the drivers, and a tabu-search algorithm to solve it, showing that familiarity-based assignments improve efficiency when familiar customers are geographically clustered.

3 SmartDelivery Architecture

SmartDelivery is designed as a layered architecture (Fig. 1). The *Data Layer (DL)* serves as the foundation of the system, collecting real-world information and transmitting it to the *Processing Layer (PL)*, which processes this data to generate route plans. The *Application Layer (AL)* manages communication between the PL and external entities. The *DL* comprises three data sources: (1) a proprietary IoT device (*SmartPos*) installed on each fleet vehicle, providing continuous real-time positional data. (2) An IoT network periodically transmitting real-time delivery metrics (e.g., fuel consumption, cargo temperature,

Fig. 1. Overview of the architecture. $\varphi_1 \dots \varphi_n$: VRP algorithms

diagnostics). (3) Other data sources, including driver feedback via a mobile app, historical delivery data, parking restriction information, and traffic limitation zones. The *PL* transforms raw data into optimized route plans through specialized modules. The *SmartPos Data Processing module (A)* preprocesses location data and forwards it to the *Updating Block*, which converts it into accurate travel times to be used as input for the selected CVRP algorithm. It also implements the sixth sense-based routing assignment. The *ML-based Algorithm Selection Block (C)* predicts the most appropriate heuristic or metaheuristic from a predefined portfolio based on the CVRP instance characteristics. The *Other Data Processing Module (B)* processes all collected data and feeds it into an *ML-based Decision Support System (DSS)* that extracts valuable insights (e.g., real-time traffic patterns, customer behaviour analysis, delay pattern identification) to provide decision-making capabilities to the system. A continuously expanding database improves DSS effectiveness. These modules, along with the supplementary data sources in the DL, are highlighted with dotted lines as they are not scheduled for short-term implementation. The *AL* provides a *web dashboard* for logistics managers to monitor deliveries, receive alerts, communicate with drivers or visualize DSS insights. Additionally, it includes a *mobile app* for drivers, which displays updated routes and stops, facilitates communication with managers, and allows drivers to submit feedback on deliveries or report issues. The following subsections detail each component of the PL, which is the system's core.

3.1 ML-Based Algorithm Selection for CVRP

The AS process, typically performed manually by domain experts, requires a deep understanding of the advantages/disadvantages of various algorithms in relation to a specific CVRP instance's class. This knowledge, hard to acquire and increasingly complex as the algorithm portfolio expands, introduces issues

such as biases in algorithm comparisons and unreproducible results. As part of SmartDelivery, we propose to develop an *Automated AS* using ML. Let \mathcal{C} be the set of all CVRP instances, $\mathcal{A} = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_m\}$ be a set of m algorithms, and $P: \mathcal{C} \times \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ a performance measure. We seek a mapping $S: \mathcal{C} \rightarrow \mathcal{A}$ such that:

$$S(c) = \arg \min_{a \in \mathcal{A}} P(c, a) \quad \forall c \in \mathcal{C} \quad (1)$$

To approximate S using ML, we need to define a feature extraction function $F: \mathcal{C} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$, which maps instances to n -dimensional feature vectors, and train an ML model $M: \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathcal{A}$ so that $M(F(c)) \approx S(c)$. The quality of M is assessed by how closely it replicates the optimal selection S . As a *case study*, to ensure both practical relevance and computational feasibility, we focus on instances ranging from 30 to 200 customers, reflecting small to medium-sized urban delivery scenarios. We employ a modified version of the instance generator script developed by Queiroga et al. [15] to produce training, validation, and testing CVRP instances. The generator systematically varies key attributes — including depot placement, customer distribution, demand patterns, and route-length distributions, as well as travel times between destinations, simulating both spatial geometries and dynamic travel conditions. A selected portfolio of state-of-the-art heuristic and metaheuristic benchmark algorithms will solve instances. Due to the computational effort required, the number of algorithms in the portfolio is limited to 10. For each instance, following multiple studies ([17], [8]), we extract a comprehensive *feature set* that captures the multidimensional characteristics of CVRP problems. Besides including the basic problem properties such as the number of customers, depot position, minimum number of vehicles required and demand statistics, we consider metrics capturing spatial distribution patterns of customers (e.g., number of clusters, distance between different clusters, and dispersion measures) and graph-based features. We apply correlation analysis to eliminate features that are highly correlated or redundant and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to reduce dimensionality. To label each CVRP instance in our dataset, we designate as the *best solver* the algorithm that achieves the lowest solution cost among our portfolio or, in case of equal costs, the solver with the shortest execution time. We train several classifiers, chosen for their diverse learning paradigms to build a robust AS module: (1) K-Nearest Neighbor with Leave-One-Out Cross Validation (LOOCV) to capture local patterns in the feature space; Random Forest with LOOCV to handle feature interactions and non-linearities, XGBoost with 5-Fold Cross Validation, which excels at handling complex non-linear relationships and Decision Trees with 5-Fold Cross Validation for interpretable decision boundaries; Multi-Layer Perceptron with 5-Fold Cross Validation for its ability to learn complex patterns. As the last step, we measure each classifier’s performance using standard metrics, including precision, recall, and F-scores, as well as evaluation protocols commonly adopted in AS studies. We also conduct an instance space analysis to identify regions where specific algorithms consistently outperform others or areas where the performance difference between the best and second-best algorithms is minimal.

3.2 Real-Time Travel Data Utilization

A significant limitation of traditional CVRP solvers is their reliance on static travel time estimates derived from geographic information systems (GIS) or open maps. These estimates often fail to capture the dynamic nature of urban environments, where travel conditions fluctuate due to traffic congestion, weather events, road construction, and other factors, leading to inaccurate route planning. SmartDelivery overcomes this limitation by collecting real travel time data and processing them through the SmartDelivery cloud. Data is gathered from SmartPos devices installed on each fleet vehicle, ensuring accurate and continuously updated estimates. In the following, we explain how the approach works. Specifically, let T_{ij} represent the generic travel time observation from destination i to destination j . To capture the varying travel time patterns at different times of day, the system maintains and continuously update a set of buffers $\{\mathcal{B}_{ij,1}, \mathcal{B}_{ij,2}, \dots\}$, where each buffer corresponds to an array of recent observations at a specific time window (e.g., morning, afternoon, evening). More formally, for a given window k we define the related buffer as an array:

$$\mathcal{B}_{ij,k} = (T_{ij,k}^{(1)}, T_{ij,k}^{(2)}, \dots, T_{ij,k}^{(m_k)}) \quad (2)$$

where $T_{ij,k}^{(1)}$ is the oldest observation in that buffer and $T_{ij,k}^{(m_k)}$ the most recent. When a new travel time T_{ij} arrives, the system identifies the relevant window k based on the timestamp and appends the new value to $\mathcal{B}_{ij,k}$. If this buffer is already full, the oldest entry is discarded before insertion. The system uses the buffer $\mathcal{B}_{ij,k}$ to calculate the estimate of the travel time between the destination i and the destination j in a particular window k using a *Linearly Weighted Moving Average (LWMA)*, to mitigate the impacts of random fluctuations and give greater importance to the most recent data:

$$\text{LWMA}_{ij,k} = \frac{\sum_{\nu=1}^{m_k} \nu T_{ij,k}^{(\nu)}}{\sum_{\nu=1}^{m_k} \nu}. \quad (3)$$

We use LWMA because it is straightforward to implement. Still, more sophisticated approaches can be used. To startup the process, we gather the initial values of travel times from open maps or GIS.

3.3 Sixth Sense-Based Route Assignment

We introduce the concept of *sixth sense* as a quantifiable measure of driver efficiency at specific destinations, based on the intuition that familiarity with locations, established customer relationships, experience with local challenges and other factors can significantly reduce drivers' service times, while not modifying the travel-cost component optimized by the CVRP solver. For each driver $d \in D$

(the set of all drivers) and destination $i \in I$ (the set of all destinations), we define the sixth sense ϕ_i^d as a weighted sum of several components:

$$\phi_i^d = \begin{cases} w_1 \left(\frac{ST_i^{\min}}{ST_i^d} \right) + w_2(CR_{i,d}) + w_3(MS_{i,d}) + \dots & \text{if } ST_i^d > 0, \\ w_2(CR_{i,d}) + w_3(MS_{i,d}) + \dots & \text{if } ST_i^d = 0. \end{cases} \quad \forall i \in I, d \in D. \quad (4)$$

ST_i^d is the service time the driver d spends at destination i and ST_i^{\min} is the minimum service time spent by any driver at destination i . $CR_{i,d}$ (Customer Rating) is an optional rating from the customer for driver d at i while $MS_{i,d}$ (Merchandise Specialty) indicates how much the driver d is skilled at handling the type of goods delivered to i . Additional factors could be introduced. The coefficients w_1, w_2, w_3, \dots weight each factor in the final sixth sense value. For simplicity, in SmartDelivery we set all the factors to zero, obtaining:

$$\phi_i^d = \begin{cases} \frac{ST_i^{\min}}{ST_i^d}, & \text{if } ST_i^d > 0, \\ 0, & \text{if } ST_i^d = 0. \end{cases} \quad \forall i \in I, d \in D. \quad (5)$$

This yields sixth sense values in the range $(0, 1]$, where 1 indicates optimal performance (the driver achieves the historically shortest service time), and 0 indicates that the driver has not yet visited the destination. In this last case $ST_i^d = 0$. Since a route $p \in P$ (the set of all programmed routes) consists of d_p destinations, we define the *route-level sixth sense* ϕ_p^d as the *simple average* of the individual ϕ_i^d over all $i \in p$:

$$\phi_p^d = \frac{\sum_{i \in p} \phi_i^d}{d_p}, \quad \forall p \in P, d \in D. \quad (6)$$

However, while the simple average is easy to interpret, it can cause drawbacks as large routes may artificially drive up or down the average, or a single outlier can skew the entire result. An alternative approach is the *Weighted average*:

$$\phi_p^d = \frac{\sum_{i \in p} w_i \phi_i^d}{\sum_{i \in p} w_i}, \quad (7)$$

where each destination i has a weight w_i . It can emphasize specific destinations more, but requires non-trivial estimation of weights w_i .

Another option is to use the *Mean penalized by variance*:

$$\phi_p^d = \frac{\sum_{i \in p} \phi_i^d}{d_p} - \lambda \sigma(\{\phi_i^d : i \in p\}) \quad (8)$$

where $\sigma(\cdot)$ is the standard deviation of the set $\{\phi_i^d : i \in p\}$, and $\lambda > 0$ controls how strongly we penalize routes where a driver's performance varies significantly across destinations. It has the advantage of discouraging drivers who

are extremely good on some stops but very poor on others, at the cost of extra parameter λ and more complex data. Other specialized metrics can be adopted in certain cases. In our SmartDelivery prototype, to facilitate the analysis we adopt the *simple average* of the ϕ_i^d values over each route. We can formulate the route assignment process as an Integer Programming (IP) problem:

$$\max \sum_{p \in P} \sum_{d \in D} \phi_p^d \cdot x_p^d \quad (9a)$$

$$\sum_{p \in P} x_p^d \leq 1, \quad \forall d \in D \quad (9b)$$

$$\sum_{d \in D} x_p^d = 1, \quad \forall p \in P \quad (9c)$$

$$x_p^d \in \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall p \in P, d \in D \quad (9d)$$

(9a) maximizes the total sixth sense across all drivers, while (9b) and (9c) respectively ensure that each driver is assigned at most one route and each route is assigned to exactly one driver. The binary decision variables are defined in 9d ($x_p^d = 1$ if route p is assigned to driver d , 0 otherwise). To obtain the service-time data required for calculating the sixth sense values, drivers must record arrival/departure times at each destination using a dedicated mobile app (future developments may automate the process). Sixth sense values are dynamically updated to improve route assignment over time; whenever a new minimum service time at a destination is recorded, all sixth sense values for that destination are recalculated accordingly. The sixth sense-based route assignment is integrated with the CVRP solver: initially, the solver computes optimized routes, by considering vehicle capacity constraints and real-time travel data. These routes are then allocated to individual drivers using the sixth sense optimization model.

4 Conclusion and future work

This paper presented SmartDelivery, a novel IoT- and ML-based platform for optimizing LMD. Specifically, it proposed an ML-based approach for dynamically selecting the most appropriate algorithm from a portfolio of heuristics and metaheuristics based on specific CVRP instance characteristics. Moreover, it described a new methodology to leverage real-time vehicle data from IoT devices to improve travel time estimates and formulated a “sixth sense” metric to account for driver expertise in the route assignment process. Currently, SmartDelivery has been described at a conceptual and architectural level but has not yet been fully implemented. The next phase involves constructing a functional prototype, allowing us to evaluate performance metrics and refine the proposed methodologies. Preliminary results suggest SmartDelivery can improve LMD efficiency, reduce costs, and mitigate negative externalities. As e-commerce continues to expand and urban environments become increasingly complex, novel approaches to LMD optimization such as SmartDelivery will become essential for sustainable logistics in the smart cities of the future.

Acknowledgments. Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

References

1. Feature and Algorithm Selection for Capacitated Vehicle Routing Problems, Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol. 5805. ESANN, Belgium (2019), <https://www.elen.ucl.ac.be/Proceedings/esann/esannpdf/es2019-110.pdf>
2. Achá, R.J.A., Goldschmidt, O., Hochbaum, D.S., Huerta, I.I.: Fast algorithms for the capacitated vehicle routing problem using machine learning selection of algorithm's parameters. In: KDIR. pp. 29–39 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.5220/0011405400003335>
3. Cao, J., Zhang, J., Liu, M., Yin, S., An, Y.: Green logistics of vehicle dispatch under smart iot. *Sensors and Materials* **34**(8), 3317–3338 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.18494/SAM3934>
4. Clarke, G., Wright, J.W.: Scheduling of vehicles from a central depot to a number of delivery points. *Operations Research* **12**, 568–581 (1964). <https://doi.org/10.1287/opre.12.4.568>
5. Deng, M., Ding, Y.: Driver-centric urban logistics optimization: vehicle routing with heterogeneous fixed drivers. *International Transactions in Operational Research* (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1111/itor.13619>
6. Erdoğan, S., Miller-Hooks, E.: A green vehicle routing problem. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review* **48**(1), 100–114 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tre.2011.08.001>
7. Herrera-Granda, I.D., Cadena-Echeverría, J., León-Jácome, J.C., Herrera-Granda, E.P., Chavez Garcia, D., Rosales, A.: A heuristic procedure for improving the routing of urban waste collection vehicles using arcgis. *Sustainability* **16**(13) (2024). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16135660>
8. Jiang, H., Wang, Y., Tian, Y., Zhang, X., Xiao, J.: Feature construction for meta-heuristic algorithm recommendation of capacitated vehicle routing problems. *ACM Trans. Evol. Learn. Optim.* **1**(1) (Apr 2021). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3447540>
9. Kim, S., Lewis, M., White, C.: Optimal vehicle routing with real-time traffic information. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems* **6**(2), 178–188 (2005). <https://doi.org/10.1109/TITS.2005.848362>
10. Konstantakopoulos, G.D., Gayialis, S., Kechagias, E.: Vehicle routing problem and related algorithms for logistics distribution: a literature review and classification. *Operational Research* pp. 1–30 (07 2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12351-020-00600-7>
11. Kotthoff, L., Gent, I.P., Miguel, I.: An evaluation of machine learning in algorithm selection for search problems. *AI Communications* **25**(3), 257–270 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.3233/AIC-2012-0533>
12. Li, R., Cheng, C., Qi, M., Lai, W.: Design of dynamic vehicle routing system based on online map service. In: 2016 13th International Conference on Service Systems and Service Management (ICSSSM). pp. 1–5 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSSSM.2016.7538425>

13. Montoya-Torres, J.R., López Franco, J., Nieto Isaza, S., Felizzola Jiménez, H., Herazo-Padilla, N.: A literature review on the vehicle routing problem with multiple depots. *Computers & Industrial Engineering* **79**, 115–129 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cie.2014.10.029>
14. Pillac, V., Gendreau, M., Guéret, C., Medaglia, A.L.: A review of dynamic vehicle routing problems. *European Journal of Operational Research* **225**(1), 1–11 (2013). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2012.08.015>
15. Queiroga, E., Sadykov, R., Uchoa, E., Vidal, T.: 10,000 optimal cvrp solutions for testing machine learning based heuristics. In: *AAAI-22 workshop on machine learning for operations research (ML4OR)* (2021)
16. Ranieri, L., Digiesi, S., Silvestri, B., Roccotelli, M.: A review of last mile logistics innovations in an externalities cost reduction vision. *Sustainability* **10**(3) (2018). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10030782>
17. Rasku, J., Kärkkäinen, T., Musliu, N.: Feature Extractors for Describing Vehicle Routing Problem Instances. In: Hardy, B., Qazi, A., Ravizza, S. (eds.) *5th Student Conference on Operational Research (SCOR 2016)*. Open Access Series in Informatics (OASICs), vol. 50, pp. 7:1–7:13. Schloss Dagstuhl – Leibniz-Zentrum für Informatik, Dagstuhl, Germany (2016). <https://doi.org/10.4230/OASICs.SCOR.2016.7>
18. Savelsbergh, M.W.P., Sol, M.: The General Pickup and Delivery Problem. *Transportation Science* **29**(1), 17–29 (February 1995). <https://doi.org/10.1287/trsc.29.1.17>
19. Schneider, M.: The vehicle-routing problem with time windows and driver-specific times. *European Journal of Operational Research* **250**(1), 101–119 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2015.09.015>
20. Solomon, M.M.: Algorithms for the vehicle routing and scheduling problems with time window constraints. *Operations Research* **35**(2), 254–265 (1987). <https://doi.org/10.1287/opre.35.2.254>
21. Toth, P., Vigo, D.: *The Vehicle Routing Problem*. Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics (2002). <https://doi.org/10.1137/1.9780898718515>
22. Tuzun, D., Magent, M.A., Burke, L.I.: Selection of vehicle routing heuristic using neural networks. *International Transactions in Operational Research* **4**, 211–221 (1997). [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0969-6016\(97\)00006-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0969-6016(97)00006-3)
23. Wanganoo, L., Patil, A.: Preparing for the smart cities: Iot enabled last-mile delivery. In: *2020 Advances in Science and Engineering Technology International Conferences (ASET)*. pp. 1–6 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ASET48392.2020.9118197>
24. Wolpert, D., Macready, W.: No free lunch theorems for optimization. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation* **1**(1), 67–82 (1997). <https://doi.org/10.1109/4235.585893>
25. Xiao, Y., Zhao, Q., Kaku, I., Xu, Y.: Development of a fuel consumption optimization model for the capacitated vehicle routing problem. *Computers & Operations Research* **39**(7), 1419–1431 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cor.2011.08.013>
26. Zhang, H., Ge, H.W., Yang, J., Tong, Y.: Review of vehicle routing problems: Models, classification and solving algorithms. *Archives of Computational Methods in Engineering* **29**, 195–221 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11831-021-09574-x>